

P4-assisted Seamless Migration of Serverless Applications Towards the Edge Continuum

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Abstract

Serverless computing has recently been presented as an effective technology for handling short-lived compute tasks in the cloud. It has the potential of becoming an attractive option also in the context of edge computing where resource-aware deployment, constrained by both limited edge computing resources and experienced latency, plays a vital role.

In this paper, we present and experimentally validate a framework that oversees serverless applications in an edge computing scenario. It completely automates serverless application deployment and provides hitless dynamic migration of application compute tasks between a pair of edge nodes, paving the way for handling significantly more complex cases. The framework relies on an integrated deployment, monitoring and offloading infrastructure that enhances AWS IoT Greengrass features and performance. Our implementation provides two separate options for relocating compute tasks by steering application traffic towards the most suitable node. One builds on an on-the-fly application component reconfiguration, while the other selects the suitable node through P4 in-network processing of resource metrics emitted by the nodes.

Our experimental demonstration evaluates the migration performance using a latency-sensitive application decomposed to serverless functions. Results reveal extremely fast dynamic reconfiguration and traffic rerouting operations. The used methods avoid congestion peaks at the edge and show no end-to-end latency increase upon migration between the nodes.

Keywords: serverless, FaaS, edge, AWS Lambda, AWS Greengrass, P4

1. Introduction

While some components of resource-hungry virtual, augmented or mixed reality and automotive applications (to name a few popular cases) can be deployed to cloud resources, due to their latency-sensitive nature, they cannot easily leverage the full potential of the cloud [1, 2] that offers virtually limitless compute power. Recent advances in pushing resources closer to end-users or data sources using edge or fog compute nodes point towards an infrastructure where we can have multiple steps in the continuum from the edge towards the cloud that gradually offer more compute power while transfer latency also increases. As edge nodes are still resource limited, managing

them efficiently is crucial for providing services adequately [3]. In recent years, serverless computing, a technology used for handling short-lived compute tasks, has gained traction as a possibility for tackling this issue. While serverless is most prominent in cloud environments, it has already found its way for applications running over an edge or fog infrastructure [4, 5, 6, 7].

Serverless computing, and its most prominent implementation, Function as a Service (FaaS), dates back to 2014 when Amazon Web Services (AWS) introduced their Lambda service [8]. Soon other big players (Microsoft, Google, IBM) followed suit by starting their own services [9, 10, 11] and open-source implementations appeared as well [12, 13]. The name hints at the high-level abstraction the concept offers: developers need to submit only the code or executable to run, specify the amount of resources to be used and the service handles everything else. While servers do run the code, developers need not worry about infrastructure aspects at all. Serverless function (units of operations) instances are started up on-demand when requests arrive to them. The execution platform can start up multiple instances simultaneously and terminate them when they are not needed anymore, providing great scaling features and sparing resources. (To guarantee flexible scaling, functions need to be stateless or properly externalize their states.) These scaling and resource management features are highly useful in edge environments as well.

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While this abstraction certainly helps running compute tasks at the edge, retaining network traffic management features can bring further advantages. In this aspect, P4-enabled switching equipment can provide flexible network traffic configuration. The P4 (Programming Protocol-Independent Packet Processors [14]) language and forwarding technology give an open programming interface to network switches with which traffic steering can be customized. The programmability is implemented via a custom pipeline supporting configurable packet headers, configurable match-action tables, programmable actions, metadata extraction, and stateful objects. This way, complex packet manipulation and processing procedures, currently not available in standard switches, can be effectively implemented even at wire speed, without the intervention of the network controller. P4 has been successfully applied in the development of several in-network functions. They include monitoring and telemetry solutions (e.g., in-band telemetry - INT), hardware acceleration of 5G network functions [15, 16, 17], dynamic scheduling for low-latency applications [18, 19, 20], and cyber-security operations [16, 21].

In this work, we combine the serverless and network programming (P4) technologies in order to work towards seamlessly running application components in the edge cloud continuum. In our view, such a combination of technologies brings synergies, however, it remains less explored in the related literature. While in previous work [22] we investigated application component offloading from the edge to the cloud, here we direct our attention to the edge domain. With the addition of novel extensions and offloading capabilities, our system still retains its previous cloud deployment capabilities. We focus on proactive applications that can access external data sources but trigger themselves, i.e., all requests initiating function instances come internally from the application, not from an external entity. We provide virtual migration leveraging the on-demand nature of the deployed serverless functions: we deploy the same function to multiple infrastructure nodes and quickly switch between them. Using the serverless feature set, function instances only consume CPU resources when they serve requests. Otherwise, they enter an idle state where no CPU is used, however, they keep their memory content from the previous invocation cached. Idle functions can be shut down after use by the execution environment based on resource availability policies. Thus, in setups where memory resources are scarce, function startups can be delayed until the application has to serve its first request, or an offloading event happens, and idle functions can be terminated frequently. However, in scenarios where constant low application latency is a requirement, with a memory trade-off, functions can be warmed up in advance as the first execution of a function can take significantly more time than subsequent ones. In this paper, we focus on this latter case by significantly extending our previous offload facilities [23] with an even faster P4-assisted mechanism and function warm-up capabilities.

We leverage AWS services (Lambda, Greengrass v1 [24]) as execution environments, and refine our deployment and migration architecture to present four main contributions. First, we introduce the novel warm-up toolset provided by our environment. Warm-up in serverless is a crucial concept when

latency is of concern. In the cloud, providers have recently started to give simple options for customized provisioning of warmed-up instances, however, at the edge this feature is still most neglected even for simpler cases than ours. Second, we give a detailed description of our higher-level offload controller that interacts with the application itself. Third, we present a previously unexplored approach for offloading combining serverless and Software Defined Networking (SDN) concepts in our lower-level offload controller (realized using P4) that directly interacts with the network infrastructure. Fourth, we evaluate the warm-up and offloading mechanisms using an application inspired by vehicle remote control.

To present these contributions, we structure this paper in the following manner. Sec. 2 reviews related work from the area of serverless computing and leveraging P4 in edge scenarios. Then we present a high-level view on our deployment and offload control architecture in Sec. 3. We follow this with detailed descriptions on our deployment and operation frameworks with function warm-up mechanisms in Sec. 4. Later, we discuss the details of our two independent offload controllers in Sec. 5. After this, Sec. 6 describes our test environment and sample application. It also provides the evaluation of our offload controller implementations taking advantage of warmed-up serverless function instances. While our concept is applicable to edge infrastructures with multiple nodes, for the sake of simplicity, we limit the evaluation to situations where two main edge nodes (one for normal operation, the other as backup) are utilized. At the end of this paper, we summarize our results and mark out possible future directions to follow in Sec 7.

2. Related work

2.1. Serverless and previous work

As discussed previously, one of the main serverless offerings is AWS Lambda. It offers on-demand functions in the cloud through built-in and custom execution environments that allow simple code upload (that is injected into the environment) or the invocation of pre-built Docker images. Functions have a single entry point (called handler function) with two arguments: a JSON event and an AWS service-specific context object. The service has a single adjustable resource parameter, the memory, that also affects the CPU allocation. Lambda does not offer accessible interfaces for function placement, only the execution region (AWS data center) can be selected. Function instances are started up in a fully managed fashion, thus, users cannot assign data center servers directly to the instances. Load-balancing and function termination is also managed by the service. A recent extension of the model provides warm-up capabilities that starts up the specified number of instances after deployment. These instances can react to incoming requests faster, eliminating the cold start of uninitialized instances.

AWS IoT Greengrass extends Lambda function execution capabilities to user-owned hardware as well, primarily focusing on IoT use cases. Using the service, IoT devices (e.g., sensors) can transmit data to a local processing unit (i.e., an edge node) which can pre-process or aggregate data using the

locally available Lambda functions before transmission to the cloud. Version 2 of the service has recently been released and while it is a major redesign, basic functionality is still the same. The built-in execution environment provides an option for running cloud Lambdas without any modifications (limited to certain programming languages). At the edge, the service limits memory access to the defined values but grants full access to the CPU. It also offers an option for creating long-lived functions besides the standard on-demand ones as well. Long-lived functions serve as a means for creating proactive applications: they run in a single instance, can run indefinitely and read sensors or trigger other on-demand Lambda functions but cannot be triggered externally using the built-in mechanisms. Greengrass provides a clear hierarchy where the cloud message broker (using the MQTT protocol) distributes messages between edge nodes, i.e., there is no direct communication between the nodes. While an edge-deployed function has a version in the cloud as well, the service does not provide built-in mechanisms for offloading to that or moving functions between edge nodes. The service does not provide warm-up capabilities either.

There is also academic research interest in serverless. Our 3-page conference paper [23] explores the deployment and network latency-triggered (collected via P4 INT) migration of such applications on edge nodes using Greengrass. Here, we extend our architecture and provide the details of our high-level offloader. We also add novel warm-up and P4-based offload capabilities complete with their detailed evaluation using node CPU load as an offload trigger. Over cloud resources, Kotless [25] provides a provider-agnostic overlay for deploying Kotlin applications and DIFFUSE [26] offers a high-level toolset for combining multiple serverless functions into a working application. In the edge domain, LaSS [27] and PAPS [28] focus on latency-sensitive applications and try to place functions and allocate resources to them so that a specified latency limit can be satisfied. LaSS offers a queuing-based allocation and auto-scaling mechanism, while in the case of PAPS, a partitioning algorithm is used in situations when workloads dynamically change and may even near overload levels. The former is implemented using the OpenWhisk [12], the latter using the OpenFaaS [13] serverless platform, both leveraging a Kubernetes container orchestrator. DFaaS [29] provides similar load balancing features. It uses a peer-to-peer overlay network for managing node memberships and balances based on load prediction relying on collected node resource utilization metrics. The tool is also implemented on an OpenFaaS basis. Akhtar *et al.* [30] provide heuristics for placing chains of serverless functions on edge environments where clients connect over mmWave wireless links. Ascigil *et al.* [31] and Rausch *et al.* [32] also deal with resource allocations in serverless edge environments using a Kubernetes basis, while the latter also takes into account the heterogeneity of infrastructure nodes (e.g., those having GPU acceleration).

Speeding up function executions by eliminating the cold start phase or offloading them to more adequate nodes is also in the focus of academic research. Silva *et al.* [33] discuss a technique that creates snapshots from function instances and restores them when terminated instances are requested again. They manage to decrease function load time to $\sim 54\text{--}84$ ms

with functions of $\sim 3\text{--}41$ MB. Sethunath *et al.* [34] propose a solution where requests are routed either to the cloud or to the edge depending on where warmed-up instances are available for serving them. However, the solution is still affected by the cold start problem at application startup or after clearing up function instances.

Baresi *et al.* [5] design a complete serverless edge platform, on the basis of OpenWhisk, that also incorporates offloading capabilities between nodes. They achieve a platform overhead in request processing latency of ~ 15 ms in the best case. Yao *et al.* [35] consider offloading computation tasks from IoT devices to a serverless edge using a technique based on deep reinforcement learning for determining the offload strategy. Ko *et al.* [36] propose offloading from IoT devices to the cloud using a method that guarantees completion latency while also minimizing the energy expenses of the devices. In a vehicular fog computing environment, CODE-V [37] optimizes compute task placement and offloading considering service latency. While these works evaluate platform contribution to latency and report them to be ~ 250 ms in the best case, results cannot be translated to application latency increase in an offloading scenario in a straightforward manner.

2.2. P4

Software-defined architectures and workflows to perform edge-to-edge or fog-to-fog node offloading orchestrated by the SDN controller have been proposed in the literature [38]. However, the scalability concerns introduced by a centralized controller are pushing the research on SDN towards the data plane programmability, exploiting in-network functions. In this regard, the P4 language represents the most utilized framework due to its flexibility, high-level and platform-agnostic approach and the increasing availability of P4-aware programmable backends (bare metal switches, smart NIC, FPGA).

The P4 potentials for data plane programmability in edge-centered networks have been detailed in the literature, mainly targeting traffic engineering solutions, cyber security applications [16], 5G/6G and softwarized networking [39], and latency-sensitive networking [19]. In-network functions specifically targeting edge computing have been proposed for traffic differentiation purposes and fine-grained telemetry [40].

Focusing on P4-based in-network, the deployment of a family of functions for the industrial IoT and edge ecosystem have been discussed in [41]. In-network caching, security, consensus protocols and streaming processes are conveniently handled at the data plane resorting to a network of cooperating switches. The paper proposes a mechanism to translate a complex operation set into a wider set of P4 match-action flow entries. The work in [42] proposes augmented in-band telemetry to provide extra information on the wireless access mobile environment (i.e., segment/end-to-end latency combined with location tracking) for dynamic network-aware traffic steering at both the user equipment and the edge switches.

A number of recent works target the utilization of P4 for Virtual Network Function (VNF) offloading. The works in [43] and in [44] propose two design methodologies for implementing multiple network functions and related chains inside a P4

switch. The work in [45] improves service function chaining performance by implementing P4 segment routing at the switches and single-root input/output virtualization at the hosts. A similar work in [46] considers the use of P4 to decompose the execution of pre-programmed VNFs inside a network processor using a multi-level chaining scheme with the goal of optimizing resource allocation. Similarly, the work in [47] proposes the recirculation of functions over a programmable data plane along with a service function chain manager performing the function placement and ordering with the goal of minimizing the chain execution completion time.

P4 solutions have also been proposed to handle serverless applications focusing on latency reduction within nodes. The work in [48] implements parallel serverless applications directly inside ASIC-based smart NICs, thus enabling overall network-centric offload of serverless computing functions at the network data plane [49]. Similarly, relocation of dispatch and orchestration services to smart NICs in FaaS environments has been proposed in the work in [50].

3. Proposed architecture for network-assisted migration of serverless applications in edge environments

In our view, providing seamless relocation of compute tasks performed by application components between different infrastructure resources involves multiple aspects right from the application’s deployment phase. We argue that application packaging, the execution environment, performance monitoring and offloading components all play crucial roles in this task. In accordance with these, the high-level view of our proposed architecture, depicted in Fig. 1, identifies three main components. The *i) Serverless Deployment Engine (SDE)* transforms application code to deployable packages and, via the infrastructure provider’s API, sets them up on the specified resources. During this process, the SDE also paves the way for the other two components by extending the application with proper interfaces. The *ii) Telemetry Service (TS)* exploits one of these interfaces for collecting infrastructure and application-level monitoring information which it feeds to the *iii) Offload Controller (OC)* that can perform reconfiguration on two levels to realize offloading functionality. On a higher, application level, the OC leverages the application reconfiguration interface installed by the SDE, to divert in-application calls. On a lower, infrastructure level, the OC can switch forwarding paths in the infrastructure which is made possible by the shared *edge infrastructure setup information* between the SDE and the OC. In this section, we provide the high-level concept of these architectural components and we discuss them in more detail in Sec. 4–5.2.

As the first step, the *application* and *setup specifications* are submitted to the SDE to specify which application component should be deployed on what infrastructure element. We assume that application-level components are available prepared for deployment as serverless artifacts, thus having single, separate entry points that can handle events arriving from other components. As part of the application’s description, the SDE receives three main elements. *i)* The application’s *structure*, i.e.,

Figure 1: High-level architecture overview.

the identifier of each individually deployable application component that is used for marking elements to package together and their invocation hierarchy. *ii) Variables* used for operating the application are also submitted to the SDE. For packaging the components, the SDE is also assumed to have complete access to *iii) the application’s code*. Among the *setup specifications*, we define how to package the application’s code and where to run it. As the *layout*, we define how application-level components are to be mapped to deployable serverless functions. Additionally, we specify what *resource* (CPU and memory) *sizes* we assign to those serverless functions and on what infrastructure nodes we deploy them. We allow the *placement* of a serverless function to multiple locations: simultaneously in the cloud and at an edge node or to multiple edge nodes. Conceptually, we leverage a *provider* that is able to cover the complete edge/cloud continuum for deployment purposes. We assume that selecting individual nodes for code execution (based on *edge infrastructure setup information*) is possible at the edge. Inversely, in a cloud scenario, we assume a fully managed infrastructure on which such selection is not available to our deployment engine. As part of the setup directives, we also submit the location of used *datastores* and a mapping specifying which datastore is used to store each application function variable. In order to prepare the application for fast startup, the expected number of functions to be *warmed-up* is specified as well. While the application-level elements are assumed to come directly from the application’s developer or maintainer, setup specifications can be created manually or in an automated fashion. This can use a higher-level entity that optimizes the layout based on diverse objectives [51, 52] or estimates parameters by simulating application behavior under varying load [53].

Based on the submitted directives, the SDE takes application-level components, packages them into serverless functions and deploys these to the specified cloud or edge resources by accessing the *Provider API* that has low-level access to infrastructure components (see step 2 in Fig. 1). While the applica-

tion is running, the invocation between application-level components and datastore access is handled by the execution environment. The environment also collects metrics specific to these operations (rate, transmitted data sizes, latency) as well as infrastructure-level metrics (e.g., edge node CPU, memory and network performance) and pushes those to the TS (step 3). The TS serves multiple purposes: it stores the collected metrics for short and long-term, offers observability features (e.g., via dashboards) and provides the metrics to the OC (step 4). The OC observes the changes in these metrics and compares them to its internal rules. These rules define thresholds according to a specific metric or a combination of multiple ones and actions that the OC has to execute. Thresholds are defined based on knowledge on the application and expectations on metrics (e.g., latency between application components or CPU load of a certain edge node). Actions are defined based on knowledge of the same *edge infrastructure setup information* that is used for creating the application layout. One method of realizing an action is to introduce changes in the application’s invocation fabric by interacting with the execution environment (step 5). In this case, the OC effectively switches between instances of the same serverless function deployed at different locations. Our concept allows running different functionalities of the TS and the OC at different locations in the continuum. It is expected that running each of their sub-components in the cloud while the application components are executed at the edge can lead to an increase in the reaction time of the OC [22]. This can be reduced by relocating or replicating certain sub-components of the TS and the OC on the edge [23]. A further improvement can be achieved via a second method when programmable network switching equipment is used to change the forwarding rules that govern application traffic to realize an OC action (step 5). In this case, the network infrastructure diverts traffic between instances of the same serverless function deployed at different locations without interaction with the execution environment.

In the following sections, we provide a detailed description on how these offloading and warm-up mechanisms work. Sec. 4 gives a discussion on our novel method of speeding up function invocations by warming up instances after deployment. The section also gives the details on how metrics are sent to (both implementations of) the OC. Sec. 5 describes how the higher-level application reconfiguration-based offloader works and introduces our novel P4-based offloader (with its networking aspects) that induces changes right at the network infrastructure level.

4. Integrated deployment, monitoring and reconfiguration

As discussed previously, our SDE transforms application code into serverless artifacts and deploys these to edge (or cloud) resources using a provider’s API. In our implementation, we leverage AWS’s offerings relying on AWS Lambda and AWS IoT Greengrass v1 as execution environments in the cloud and at the edge, respectively. As Greengrass makes possible the use of Lambda functions outside of AWS’s infrastructure, the SDE can rely on the serverless function execution environment in both cases that we further extend for providing features required

Figure 2: Deployment, monitoring and offloading details.

by our high-level concept. The actual deployment is performed through AWS CloudFormation [54] and Greengrass which we use to access the provider API.

Fig. 2 shows a more detailed view on how the deployment works. The SDE takes the f_i application components and packages one or more of them into F_j serverless functions according to the layout specifications and assigns them to nodes (when applicable). We enable the packing of multiple application-level components into a single serverless function and the insertion of a single application-level function into multiple serverless functions. In the example shown in Fig. 2, the f_3 and f_4 application components are merged into the $F_2 = W(f_3, f_4)$ serverless function which is assigned to two edge nodes, denoted as E_1 and E_2 . During packaging, the SDE adds a W wrapper that will serve as a single entry point for F_j and extends the built-in execution environment with five main interfaces for serving warm-up, telemetry, variable access and reconfiguration functionalities, as well as invocations among application-level components. W provides two options for offering these. First, it extends events sent between application-level components with context-specific information. Second, it offers an enriched context object to each of the wrapped functions alongside the events, extending the basic AWS Lambda call arguments. Interaction from within the application component with the outside world is performed via the context object, i.e., other application-level components, variables can be reached via that.

In a usual serverless setting, we find environment variables (e.g., v_e^f in the figure) for static configuration and variables tied to datastores for more dynamic data (e.g., v_1 and v_2). The latter category can be used for storing externalized states or communication between disjoint parts of the application that do not directly invoke each other. The SDE configures W to tie environment variables and datastore access endpoints to function variables. In turn, W offers an abstraction (the *variables* inter-

face in Fig. 2) to functions for accessing environment variables, local, Redis and AnnaBellaDB [55] datastores via standardized get and set methods through the context object.

In a similar fashion, the SDE configures the wrapper of $F_j = W(f_j, \dots)$ to have connections with other $F_k = W(f_k, \dots)$ serverless functions where $f_j \rightarrow f_k$ is a possible invocation in the application’s call graph. Through its *invocation* interface, W can handle all invocations between its wrapped functions and those that are outside of its scope. As an example based on Fig. 2, the $f_1 \rightarrow f_2$ and the $f_2 \rightarrow f_3$ application-level calls are handled by the invocation interface of F_1 . The fact that $f_2 \in F_1$ and $f_3 \in F_2$, is hidden from the f_i application-level functions, they use the same method offered by the context object in both cases. F s placed in the cloud or on the same edge nodes can communicate directly with each other thanks to the AWS Lambda/Greengrass environments. In the cloud, invocations go through HTTPS API calls, at the edge they use MQTT messaging.

4.1. Telemetry

As the complete execution of an f_i application-level component is handled by a W wrapper, it can capture performance metrics on f_i . For invocations and datastore accesses, W captures their rate, the size of the carried data and the latency of the operation. In the case of invocations, W also captures blocking delay: the time it blocks the execution of f_i while it sends out an event. In order to record the invocation latency, a timestamp is added to each event which is read (and removed) by the invocation interface on the recipient side. Latency is calculated as the difference between the arrival time and said timestamp. Based on the timestamping mechanism, W also calculates the delay of handling an event from its origin (arrival at the first application component). W monitors the execution time of each wrapped f_i too with and without datastore access and blocking delays. In addition to these, W provides an option for application components to log custom metrics via the context object.

The SDE deploys a special Node Telemetry long-lived serverless function to each edge node used in the placement of the application (e.g., T_{E_1} in Fig. 2). They collect CPU and memory load information and provide measurements with an approximate frequency of 3/s. We found that this configuration offers a good trade-off between precision and CPU load, as sampling at higher frequencies adversely affects the CPU load.

All these telemetry metrics are logged to the Telemetry Service (TS) using a protocol compatible with Amazon CloudWatch Metrics. For long-term storage and data visualizations via dashboards, metrics are sent to Amazon CloudWatch. To reduce the reaction time of the Offload Controller, a short-term storage sub-component of the TS is deployed at the edge. They provide similar query interfaces and capabilities. While the cloud part is able to scale to high arrival intensities automatically, it can return metric data using a 1 s resolution as its finest setting and aggregates these to blocks spanning larger time intervals (one minute, one hour) as time progresses. The edge-based part provides only vertical scaling and is intended to sustain metrics from a relatively short (but configurable) time-

frame. However, it retains all samples and can return those during a query.

Node Telemetry components also send CPU and memory load metrics directly to our P4-driven infrastructure-level offload controller (P4OC). Metrics are carried by proprietary Edge Resource Monitoring (ERM) protocol messages that are sent to predefined layer 2 and 3 destination addresses.

4.2. Remote invocation and P4 offload control

To provide offloading capabilities to backup nodes, we leverage two options: one at the level of the layout specification, the other at the serverless function invocation level. In the layout, we specify multiple serverless functions incorporating the same application-level functions and assign each of these to different edge nodes. At the invocation level, we set up reconfigurable paths between the functions deployed to different edge nodes. In our example in Fig. 2, $F_1 = W(f_1, f_2) \mapsto E_1$ (the F_1 serverless function incorporates the f_1 and f_2 functions and is deployed to node E_1), $F_2 = W(f_3, f_4) \mapsto \langle E_1, E_2 \rangle$ (F_2 is deployed to both E_1 and E_2) and f_2 invokes f_3 . Thus we set up a way for F_1 to seamlessly call F_2 whether it is located on E_1 ($F_2^{E_1}$) or E_2 ($F_2^{E_2}$) and we make this choice configurable while the application is running.

As functions on different nodes can communicate only via the cloud in the base AWS implementation, such situations result in potentially high invocation delays. While standard Greengrass invocations within an edge node complete in 2–4 ms on average, built-in intra-node invocations can take up to hundreds of milliseconds depending on the distance from the serving AWS region and transferred data sizes [23, 56]. To significantly reduce this delay, we circumvent the built-in invocation method that always goes through the event broker set up in the cloud and introduce direct communication between the edge nodes [23]. To achieve this, we distribute broker functionality to each edge node relying on an additional serverless function and the invocation interface of the wrapper. At deployment time, the SDE adds an *Edge Relay* serverless function to each used edge node. The SDE connects these functions with all other functions on the same edge node using the standard Greengrass communication channels. The SDE also supplies a list of the used edge nodes and their IP addresses to every function wrapper so they can connect to the remote Edge Relay. The Edge Relay is a long-lived function, thus it automatically starts up as a single instance on each node and waits for incoming TCP or UDP messages that it will relay to the proper serverless function. Fig. 3 shows that, in a remote invocation case, F_i on node E_1 sends out its events using TCP or UDP to the R_{E_2} long-lived serverless function on E_2 which relays this event using the standard Greengrass communication to F_j . Latency-wise this solution has two constituents. First, the $F_i \rightarrow R_{E_2}$ invocation experiences delays usual for TCP/UDP socket communications. Second, a 2–4 ms-long component is added due to the $R_{E_2} \rightarrow F_j$ Greengrass communication. When connecting edge nodes with high-speed links and/or placing them physically close to each other, the second part can become dominant, thus we can achieve inter-edge-node communication delays comparable to intra-node invocation delays. (We note that

Figure 3: Invocation between functions located on different edge nodes.

within a deployment, either TCP or UDP can be chosen for carrying remote invocations. The selection should be made before the deployment is initiated.)

Our P4 Offload Controller takes advantage of the UDP-based forwarding. The P4 switch basically hijacks the invocations destined for the default working edge node and starts forwarding them to the backup node. When both nodes are set up with the same serverless functions, the invocations will be forwarded to the appropriate application component. We elaborate on the internals of the P4OC later, in Sec. 5.2.2. (We note that in the UDP-based relay’s case, we set the `SO_NO_CHECK` socket option to 1 at the source function to disable the UDP checksum which makes the simple hijacking mechanism possible.)

We also note that using externalized (state) data in an offloading scenario can pose latency and access problems. Let’s consider the case of $F_1 = W(f_1) \mapsto \langle E_1, E_2 \rangle$ and assume that the f_1 application-level component externalizes data to a v variable that it needs to read when it starts and write upon finishing its compute task. While f_1 runs on edge node E_1 , it is reasonable to store v on E_1 to achieve the lowest access latency. However, when the F_1 serverless function is moved to E_2 , f_1 would need to read v which is still located on E_1 . This might result in an increased access latency depending on the distance and networking conditions between E_1 and E_2 . The process is kept up until the storage location of v changes to E_2 . To illustrate the second issue, let’s also assume that $F_2 = W(f_2) \mapsto E_1$ and f_2 also reads v (f_1 and f_2 communicate via a shared variable). In order to avoid f_2 reading stale data and becoming out of sync with f_1 , changing the location of v has to happen seamlessly and simultaneously for both application components. These issues can be resolved by extending wrapper capabilities for switching between multiple datastores (instances or different options available on different edge nodes) or delegating the task to a datastore manager that can relocate data when the access pattern changes (operations start to originate from a different node). In this work, we explore the second option by relying on an access pattern-aware datastore option. We discuss the chosen tool briefly in Sec. 6.1 where we describe our experimental testbed setup.

4.3. Reconfiguration

Switching between the different invocation methods (standard or remote edge) is enabled by the RESTful *reconfiguration* interface. It accepts invocation reconfiguration messages specifying application component level invocations (from the call graph) and offload targets which can be specific edge nodes or the cloud. In the former case, events will traverse the Edge Relay on the given node, as discussed before. In the latter case, the standard AWS invocation is used that triggers a function in

the cloud [22]. For example, in the case shown in Fig. 2, as reconfiguration, we specify the $f_2 \rightarrow f_3$ invocation of the application’s call graph, and that f_3 should be looked up on E_2 .

We leverage long-lived functions for providing always accessible reconfiguration interfaces and “in-band” distribution of reconfiguration messages. Those serverless functions that wrap application components (everything besides Node Telemetry and Edge Relay), are long-lived and wrap an application component that is a root in one connected component of the application’s call graph, and are handled as recipients of reconfiguration commands. When receiving a reconfiguration command, the wrapper in the serverless functions reconfigures its own invocations based on the instructions and attaches the remaining instructions to outgoing events, in an in-band fashion. Subsequently called on-demand serverless functions act similarly: reconfigure their own invocations and forward the remaining instructions. This way, reconfiguration takes effect as the first event traverses the application after a reconfiguration message is received. Forwarding of (parts of) the reconfiguration messages is kept up until a new reconfiguration completely reverts the changes to the default determined at deployment. With each incoming event, the wrapper analyzes the received in-band reconfiguration instructions, and if there are none received, it reverts back to its defaults. This in-band distribution assures that reconfiguration (eventually) reaches all on-demand functions whether they do not have an active instance at the time of reconfiguration or have multiple ones. (We note that the reconfiguration interface offers a similar API for changing variable assignments as well.)

4.4. Warm-up

For warming up functions, we follow a similar method to the one shown for reconfiguration. The SDE copies the rate of all $f_i \rightarrow f_j$ invocations to the $F_i \ni f_i$ serverless function. The rate describes how many parallel instances of $F_j \ni f_j$ are required to handle all $f_i \rightarrow f_j$ invocations during the normal operation of the application. Right after the application is deployed, all long-lived serverless functions that wrap application components start the warm-up process. First, an F_i serverless function calls all its f_i wrapped application functions with an empty event and a special attribute in the context object specifying that the call is a warm-up. Then it executes all of its external invocations in parallel, that is, for all $f_j \notin F_i$ components where there is an $f_i \in F_i$ with an $f_i \rightarrow f_j$ invocation, it sends out a warm-up invocation. In such cases, a special field is added to the outgoing events that signifies the special intention. When the F_j on-demand wrapper of the f_j application component receives such a warm-up call, it removes the special field from the event and repeats the same process: calls all wrapped functions and executes all external invocations. Before transitioning to an idle state, F_j remains blocked for a specified amount of time. During this time, it does not perform any computations, however, it registers as being busy at the execution environment. This blocking and the parallel invocations ensure that the execution environment instantiates enough parallel instances that are needed for the normal operation of the application. To decrease instantiation delay in offloading situations as well, ex-

ternal invocations are also automatically relayed to everywhere where f_j is present: other edge nodes and the cloud.

When an $f_i \in F_i$ application component is called, its libraries and global variables are loaded automatically. As f_i is notified of the warm-up event, it can prepare specific functionality for such occasions: it can load datasets, machine learning models or initialize connections to other services, for example.

To fully leverage warm-up capabilities, invocation rates have to match those in real life and normal application operation should start only after the process is complete. However, the delay of the process is heavily dependent on the application composition and available compute resources. An upper-layer entity can take into account these aspects as well when creating the deployment layout and resource assignments, but this is out of the scope of the current work. At the edge, the Greengrass execution environment terminates idle serverless function instances only when it runs out of memory resources or reaches a specified number of concurrent functions. In the cloud, the Lambda execution environment clears up idle instances using an undisclosed algorithm. To keep instances alive in the cloud, warm-up calls need to be repeated periodically. While the wrapper implementation supports this periodic repetition, we do not discuss it further as we focus on edge deployments in this work.

5. Offload control mechanisms

Our design provides options for implementing two distinct offload control mechanisms that can act separately. They both leverage our extensions to the basic AWS IoT Greengrass communication and realize different offloading capabilities.

5.1. Node-Based Offload Controller

To perform offloading with our Node-Based Offload Controller (NBOC), we take advantage of the remote invocation capabilities and the reconfiguration interface. To reduce reaction time, the NBOC is co-located with the edge-based part of the Telemetry Service on an edge node and (contrary to the P4OC) it can directly access all telemetry metrics stored by the TS. At the end of the deployment, the SDE sends deployment data to the NBOC via a RESTful interface. This describes which serverless functions have been deployed on what edge nodes and how to reach them, as well as which application components are wrapped by these serverless functions. Through its RESTful API, the NBOC accepts the addition or deletion of rules that govern the offloading behavior. Thresholds can be set for individual metrics using different comparison operators (smaller, greater, equal, etc.). Evaluation can be set for a single or multiple samples of a given metric. In the latter case, typical functions (average, minimum, maximum, standard deviation) can be used for handling aggregations. Multiple metrics can be handled together using logical (and, or, not) operators. For each condition (set), at least one action has to be defined. The actions define which node and serverless function are to be notified and what reconfiguration message should be sent out in accordance with the format discussed in the first paragraph of Sec. 4.3. The NBOC constantly checks the metrics stored in

Figure 4: Edge Resource Monitoring (ERM) packet structure.

the co-located TS and matches them against its rules. It provides a configurable time interval between the execution of two consecutive checks. Once the NBOC finds a match for one of its rules it sends out the specified instructions to the appropriate serverless function’s reconfiguration interface. By applying invocation changes, the NBOC is able to offload computation tasks from one edge node to another (or to the cloud). (We note that actions can also specify updates to function variables as well.)

5.2. Active, stateful steering-driven P4 offload control

We realize our infrastructure-level offload controller as an SDN-based data plane programmability framework. It deploys a P4 network switch capable of steering the serverless application’s traffic based on the CPU conditions of nearby edge nodes. To accomplish the task, we propose two main innovations for the switch functionalities: processing of a novel dedicated extra-header, referred to as Edge Resource Monitoring (ERM) protocol, and stateful steering resorting to programmable memory registers.

The ERM extra-header is conceived for conveying updated edge node performance metrics to network nodes. The ERM fields (illustrated in Fig. 4) include the protocol version, the sender edge node identifier and the list of currently monitored metrics with their actual values. In our P4 Offload Controller (P4OC) implementation, the P4 switch actively listens for such messages carrying edge node CPU and memory load values, expressed in percentage. Upon receiving ERM messages destined to predetermined layer 2 and 3 addresses, the switch stores the values of the metrics inside dedicated per-edge registers.

In parallel, the switch forwards application traffic between edge nodes while also matching them against P4OC rules. Using the SDN forwarding framework, the switch is instructed to match the packet against specific protocol filters and masks and to forward traffic on pre-selected outgoing interfaces. Typical flow entries match the destination IP address of the packet with the edge node’s (or its pool’s) address which pinpoint the output port. Conversely, the traffic steering process overrules the standard forwarding based on P4OC rules that involve internal operations performed at the switch. In particular, stateful steering assigns the output port based on the internal state and value of memory registers holding edge node metrics. In this work, we consider P4OC rules that define thresholds for CPU metrics and actions that select the edge node that guarantees a predefined amount of free CPU percentage. Enacting this stateful steering, the network dynamically forwards the application traffic preventing excessive CPU usage, consequently end-to-end latency spikes, thus assuring proper application operation.

Figure 5: P4 switch internal design implementing ERM-based traffic steering.

The scheme of Fig. 5 shows the proposed design of the P4 switch enabling ERM-based steering. The switch is designed on the BMv2 backend abstract model (i.e., V1 model [57]) and encompasses a programmable parser, ingress pipeline, egress pipeline and deparser sections. Packets are received on an input interface and passed to the *parser*. The programmable parser includes the standard protocol stack dissection (Ethernet frame, IP header, UDP header) along with the novel ERM extra-header dissector, so that all packet protocol fields are read/write accessible. Then packets are passed to the *ingress pipeline* which is designed as a conditional flow table execution control. The pipeline checks if the packet encloses a valid ERM extra header. In case of doing so, packets are matched against *Table_ERM*, otherwise against *Table0*.

5.2.1. ERM packet processing

Table_ERM matches the IP source addresses and the ERM *edge_id* fields to detect the edge node from which the ERM message originates. This triggers the CPU level update of the *Edge Node State* (ENS) register and the computation of the best edge candidate. The candidate computation algorithm implements a double threshold-based hysteresis mechanism. The offload and reversal CPU thresholds (T_{offload} and T_{reversal} , respectively) are read from the dedicated *CPU Threshold* (CPUT) register. The current target edge node E_t , stored in the *Best Current Target Edge* (BCTE) register, is also queried at this point. Thresholds are compared with the current c_i CPU levels, stored in the ENS. The algorithm selects the new candidate target as hereafter described when considering a default working (E_w) and backup node (E_b):

$$\text{if } (E_t = E_w) \wedge (c_w > T_{\text{offload}}) \wedge (c_w > c_b) \text{ then } E_t \leftarrow E_b \quad (1)$$

$$\text{if } (E_t = E_b) \wedge (c_w < T_{\text{reversal}}) \text{ then } E_t \leftarrow E_w \quad (2)$$

Condition 1 shows the constraints to switch the traffic from E_w to E_b , when E_w 's CPU (c_w) exceeds the offload threshold and E_b is less loaded. Condition 2 shows the rule to revert back from the backup E_b to the working E_w upon E_w 's CPU

load decreases under the reversal threshold. In both conditions, the BCTE register is rewritten with the new computed target and the next incoming application packet will be subject to the updated steering condition. Specific *Table_ERM* flow entries configure forwarding to the candidate edge node (i.e., working or backup). The hysteresis mechanism ensures that target edge variations are not subject to CPU load transients, otherwise leading to network and application instability.

5.2.2. Application traffic processing

In the application traffic's case, packets are subject to a different flow table, *Table0*. This table enables both standard forwarding and ERM-based steering based on traffic matches. Standard forwarding is simply implemented by specifying the output port directly in the flow rule sent by the control plane API (through flow action `set_egress_port`). Conversely, for traffic subject to steering, the output port is retrieved from the BCTE register (through flow action `set_ERM_egress_port`). Moreover, packets are subject to additional processing in the egress table. First, packet destination MAC and IP addresses are overwritten with those of E_t , retrieved from the ENS registers. Then the packet is subject to checksum recomputation and update.

The switch design includes the control plane API flow rules for tables and registers. In particular, the CPU thresholds and the edge node inventory information (ENS) may be configured at bootstrap and updated at runtime. Likewise, table flow rules identify the traffic subject to standard forwarding and ERM-based forwarding.

6. Experimental results

In this section, we give a detailed discussion on the experiments that we conduct. In all cases, we use a common testbed where we utilize two nodes for running the most resource-heavy application component. We designate one node for normal operation (E_w) and one as a backup. Our application is inspired by an automotive use-case where we emulate the remote control of a vehicle. Using the application, we investigate the effects that warm-up and both of our separate offload controllers exert on key performance indicators of our application. We highlight the most important parameters of each evaluated case in Table 1. We show the number of Infer functions (the most compute-heavy function that is migrated, see Sec. 6.2), offload and reversal CPU thresholds as well as the number of CPU load samples (with collection time) that trigger the migration. We start offloading when the CPU level of E_w (averaged over the samples) reaches T_{offload} and we revert when it goes below T_{revert} .

6.1. Experimental testbed setup

Fig. 6 depicts our testbed setup that has three edge (E_0 , E_w , and E_b) and a *Control node*. The Control node is a laptop that hosts the application control functionality (discussed later in more detail), the edge-based sub-component of our Telemetry Service and the Node-Based Offload Controller. E_0 is a physical unit that has a direct connection with the vehicle. E_w hosts

Function	Deployment size [MB]
I: Connect Vehicle	1
II: Grab Image	4.1
III: Infer	24.2
IV: Control All Vehicles	1
V: Control One Vehicle	1

Node	IP address	Software stack	(v)CPUs	Memory
Control	192.168.10.108	Ubuntu 18.04, Python 3.8	8 × Intel Core i5-8250U	8 GB
E_0	192.168.10.100	Ubuntu 18.04, AWS IoT Greengrass v1.11.3	8 × Intel Xeon E5-2650 v3	6 GB
E_w	192.168.10.101	Ubuntu 18.04, AWS IoT Greengrass v1.11.3	8 × Intel Xeon E5-2650 v3	6 GB
E_b	192.168.10.102	Ubuntu 18.04, P4 BMv2	6 × Intel Xeon E5-2620	16 GB
P4 switch	N/A	Ubuntu 18.04, P4 BMv2	6 × Intel Xeon E5-2620	16 GB

Figure 6: Application decomposition and placement of components on testbed nodes.

the application’s most resource-intensive component in a normal operational case, while E_b is the backup node where we offload this resource-intensive component when E_w experiences a rise in CPU load. Both E_w and E_b are virtual machines (VM) on different physical servers. Each edge node has 8 vCPUs, 6 GB of RAM and run version 1.11.3 of AWS IoT Greengrass as the execution environment for our application on top of the Ubuntu 18.04 operating system. All nodes are connected via an optical fronthaul through a P4 software switch.

The switch realizes the design discussed in Sec. 5.2, developed as a Behavioral Model version 2 (BMv2) backend target instance. It is compiled and deployed on a server running Ubuntu 18.04, equipped with 6 CPU cores, 16 GB of RAM and 3 Gigabit Ethernet Network Interface Cards. At the switch bootstrap, a number of flow rules are enforced on the switch to tune its behavior at runtime. In particular, the CPUR registers are populated with the T_{offload} and T_{reversal} thresholds, the ENS with E_w and E_b identifiers, attached ports, IP and MAC addresses. Additionally, flow rules for $Table_{ERM}$ configure the E_w working and E_b backup target nodes. After bootstrap,

Table 1: High-level summary of the main evaluation case parameters.

Test case	No. warmed-up Infer functions	Offload		
		T_{offload}	T_{reversal}	Trigger samples
Warm-up	0, 2, 3, 4	manual control	N/A	N/A
NBOC	4	85%	40%	55 (~15 s), 1 (~1/3 s)
P4OC				1 (~1/3 s)

the switch is configured to serve as a packet forwarder for the warm-up sessions, i.e., application traffic is forwarded based on the destination IP address value. To this end, 3 $Table_0$ flow rules are enforced by the control plane API (i.e., the BMv2 switch command line interface) providing static port to target mapping using the set_egress_port flow action. When warm-up is concluded, the control plane sends a new set of flow rules. In particular, traffic received at port 1 and 2 continues to be served with standard forwarding, while traffic received at port 0 and targeting either E_w or E_b is subject to ERM-based steering, through the $set_ERM_egress_port$ flow action. At this point, the switch operates at its full functionality: ERM messages generated by all the edge nodes are matched by $Table_{ERM}$, updating the CPU load levels inside the ESN and enforcing the steering.

To mitigate the deterioration of datastore access during compute task migration (as mentioned in Sec. 4.2), we set up AnnaBellaDB (ABDB) [55] datastore instances on E_0 , E_w and E_b . ABDB is an access pattern-aware key-value store that is designed to fit serverless and offloading use-cases. It achieves delays close to or better than that of Redis on such use-cases [58], while relying on a cluster of instances that provide data placement optimization for granting low average access latency [55]. ABDB utilizes multiple child instances and a parent that holds the cluster together. It tracks read and write operations (rates, delays) at each instance and while reading and writing can be initiated at any cluster member, data is stored only at one instance. Key placement (storage of a piece of data) is determined so as to always provide the lowest access latency. Thus, in our case, the application can perform read and write operations on the same key from any of our nodes, and in the back-

ground, ABDB will resolve the requested key and seamlessly serve the request. When moving components around (offloading), ABDB recalculates the optimal placement of the affected keys, relocates them and will provide the best possible access latency again after convergence.

6.2. Experimental application decomposition and placement

Using the Serverless Deployment Engine, we deploy a remote control application on the edge infrastructure described above. The sample application, also implemented by us, considers vehicles equipped with a camera that records the road ahead and facilities that enable to remotely enable or disable their movement. We decompose the application into multiple cooperating components and manually synthesize its deployment layout that we submit to the SDE.¹ We utilize two loops: one for interpreting what the vehicle observes, and one that performs the actual remote control. We do this separation in order to provide a more constant rate for the control messages that is not influenced by the execution time of the other half of the application. In addition to the loops, we utilize an external *Vehicle Connection Manager* that can start or stop the application by supplying a list of vehicles. We implement these loops using five serverless functions in total, assigning distinct functionalities to each, as depicted in Fig. 6. *I: Connect Vehicle* is the dispatcher of the observation loop. It is a long-lived function that iterates through a list of vehicles, stored as an environment variable. The variable is filled by the Vehicle Connection Manager using the function’s reconfiguration interface (see step 1 in Fig. 6). The function dispatches each list item (a three tuple containing vehicle identifier, camera and control interfaces) to on-demand functions that perform the observational tasks (step 2). *II: Grab Image* connects to the specified vehicle’s camera interface and queries an image from it (step 3). In step 4, the function streams the grabbed image along with the vehicle’s identifier and control interface to the next function (the camera interface is not forwarded as being unnecessary at this point). *III: Infer* performs object detection (using OpenCV’s [59] Deep Neural Networks module and the MobileNet-SSD network) on the received picture and writes its results and the vehicle’s control interface to a datastore using the vehicle ID as key (step 7). *IV: Control All Vehicles* is the long-lived dispatcher of the control loop. Similarly to the Connect Vehicle function, it handles a list of vehicles that is supplied by the Vehicle Connection Manager in step 1. The function passes the individual vehicle IDs to on-demand functions in step 8. *V: Control One Vehicle* handles the single given vehicle. Using the ID, it reads the detected objects from the datastore (step 9) and investigates if there are objects falling into a category that indicate a stop condition. Based on this, it enables/disables vehicle movement using the control interface read also from the datastore (step 10). In this sample application, we use the “person” object category to signify a stop condition.

¹Source code of the decomposed application adapted to deployment with the SDE can be accessed at: <https://github.com/hsnlab/vehicle-control-sample-app>

In this test environment, we emulate the vehicle and provide a random JPEG image through the camera interface and discard the received control messages. We place this emulated vehicle on E_0 as well. To provide a sufficiently high load and rates that can be meaningful in real-life scenarios, we trigger the application’s observation loop with a frequency of 12/s and the control loop with 10/s. The functions handle warm-up events and load the used libraries at that time. The Infer function initializes the used machine learning model as well.

We deploy the Infer function to edge node E_w and E_b , configure the application to use E_w at startup and set the edge relay protocol to UDP. Thus, in step 4, Grab Image always uses a remote invocation and sends out the captured image using UDP packets. Depending on the Offload Controller’s decision, the traffic will go to E_w or E_b . Under normal load at E_w , the UDP-based remote invocations arrive to R_{E_w} (step 5a) which forwards them to their destination using the Greengrass-default MQTT channel (step 6a). In an offloaded case, steps 5b–7b are followed in the observation loop. As per discussed in Sec. 6.1, the used AnnaBellaDB instances assure that average access latency across all edge nodes is minimized after convergence [55].

The paths used by our two OC implementations are also marked in Fig. 6. The NBOC follows the A-path. At step A1, CloudWatch-compatible node metrics are sent to the TS which are read by the NBOC in step A2. The NBOC sends reconfiguration instructions to the Connect Vehicle function in step A3 which specify a change in the *Grab Image* \rightarrow *Infer* function invocations: they are executed via E_w under normal load and via E_b under increased load. The Connect Vehicle function then distributes these instructions to the Grab Image function. Rules and actions are sent to the NBOC manually. The P4OC follows the B-path: the P4 switch captures ERM messages (step B1) and diverts the application traffic accordingly (step B2).

To achieve better visual distinction, in all of our tests, we use asymmetrical initial loads at E_w and E_b . With the application deployed but not running (i.e., starting with an empty list of vehicles), E_w always has an initial CPU load of approximately 38%, while E_b has 25%. We increase this load by submitting one vehicle’s data to the application using the Vehicle Connection Manager. To initiate offloading, we execute an external CPU load generator that can push the load on E_w above the set T_{offload} threshold.

We also initialize SDE-driven deployments from the Control node. While the SDE extends the AWS deployment services’ capabilities, these are lightweight extensions that do not contribute to deployment latency [52] or resource usage significantly. The resource footprint of the local TS and the NBOC depends on the application load: in our test cases, their combined CPU load was always a fraction of a vCPU core while consuming a few tens of MB of memory. Deployed Edge Relay and Node Telemetry components also proved to be lightweight causing insignificant CPU and memory loads.

6.3. The effects of function warm-up

To highlight the benefits of warming up function instances before application startup, we conduct two types of measurements. In the first, we set a baseline and deploy the application

with warm-up capabilities disabled. In the second, we determine the optimal number of instances to be warmed-up, deploy the application by warming up those instances and compare the results to the baseline.

Fig. 7a shows the results gained when no function instances are warmed-up. The figure is split into three parts, all of them showing values registered in the TS. We visualize the data averaged using a 1 s time window, meaning, every point shown in the figure is an average of the preceding 1 s. The topmost chart portrays in-application latency characteristics. First, we display the total delay an event experiences until it is processed by the Infer function (i.e., from the time a trigger is emitted by the Connect Vehicle function until it is completely processed at the corresponding Infer function by writing its end result to the datastore). Second, the delays experienced by the two invocations in the application’s observation loop are unfolded: *Connect Vehicle* → *Grab Image* and *Grab Image* → *Infer*. Third, the latency of the *Control All Vehicles* → *Control One Vehicle* invocation is exposed. In the figure, we refer to these invocations by their receiving endpoints. The middle chart displays the CPU load on the working and backup edge nodes. The metric shows an aggregation of the values for all vCPUs scaled to the interval of 0%–100% (100% meaning all 8 vCPUs are completely loaded). Finally, the bottom-most chart illustrates the used memory on both of these edge nodes.

In this representative case, deployment of the application finishes when the test time reaches its 1st second. We submit our test vehicle configuration to the application after 44 s. At this time, the Connect Vehicle function starts emitting triggers at an approximate rate of 12/s. In response to this, the Greengrass execution environment initializes first the Grab Image, then the Infer function. As none of them have available instances at first, new function instances need to load all their packages increasing the serving time of the first trigger event. This forces the execution environment to start up more and more instances until the process stabilizes which can be deduced from the initially high but gradually decreasing invocation delays. This process adds an approximately 2 s delay between starting up at least one operational instance from each function. During this time, some trigger events also remain unhandled. Observing the total inference delay, stability is reached at the 55th second of our test, making up a complete “warm-up” delay of 11 s. The CPU utilization at E_w already starts to decrease 4 s prior to that. In the preceding time, an extremely high load is experienced. At the highest point, the additional load compared to the unloaded case reaches around 60%, achieving 91% on the absolute scale. During this hard startup process, the execution environment creates 7 instances of the Infer function at E_w occupying 473 MB of memory in total. Initially, total inference delay starts at 3.9 s and gradually decreases until it stabilizes at approximately 55 ms.

We perform a manual offload to E_b at second 72 of the test which results in a similar cascade of events on E_b . CPU usage reaches an absolute maximum of 75% (a 50% addition compared to the unloaded case) in 5 s. Average values increase again similarly to the case at E_w . Due to a part of the application (running on E_0) being already warmed-up and some in-

stances finishing execution on E_w in the first few cycles, latency and CPU peaks are slightly lower, however. Eventually, we end up with 5 instances of the Infer function started at E_b occupying 397 MB of memory in total. At the offloading point, total inference delay jumps to approximately 2 s to return to a stable 54 ms when all function instances finish their startup process. The offloading process manages to “warm-up” the Infer function instances on E_b in 5 s.

Further 10 experiments run with the same configuration resulted in a similar number of instances being started up. On E_0 , in case of Grab Image, we found 3 instances in 80% of the cases, and 4 in the rest, while for Control One, we found 2 instances in half of the experiments and 3 in the other half. On E_w , we found 7 Infer instances in 30% of the occasions, 6 in 60% and 5 in 10%. On E_b , we found 5 Infer instances in 90% of the cases and 4 in 10% of them.

To determine the optimal number of instances to warm up, we executed longer tests where we let the application run for 30 minutes after reaching stability, both at E_w and E_b . In the case of Grab Image, we measured a maximum execution time of 26 ms and 10 ms for Control One on E_0 . As for the Infer function, we measured a maximum of 78 ms at E_w and 89 ms at E_b . In the case of utilizing E_w , invocation delays were always under 10 ms. When switching to E_b , we found 99% of the invocation delays to be under 10 ms, however, in 0.17% of the cases we observed higher than 20 ms delays. On rare occasions, the rate of triggering the observation loop diverged from the set 12/s average and reached a 14/s maximum. Using a naïve calculation with these rates and delays, one can assume that two instances of the Infer function are sufficient for serving the application’s needs even during the 14/s invocation maximums. In reality, however, we still experience increased initial invocation delays (or new instances being started up) until warming up 4 instances of the Grab Image and Infer on-demand functions. In the control loop, 2 instances of the Control One Vehicle function are sufficient.

Fig. 7b shows a representative run of the manual offloading case while warming up the determined amount of instances. The warm-up phase is application specific, as it depends on the load times of the specific libraries. In our application’s case, it lasts for 37 s. Increased CPU load can be observed for 6 s in total (it is slightly shorter at E_b). This is right in between the 7 s of starting up instances without warm-up in the normal operation phase and the 5 s of the offloading case. CPU load peaks are much lower, however, on both edge nodes. The peak of the relative load increment is 19% at E_w (41% less than without warm-up) and 23% at E_b (27% less than in the comparative case). However, looking at only the graph of the CPU load is not enough for determining the completion of the warm-up process. To precisely measure its length, we have to observe the memory consumption chart as well that shows a two-stage allocation process. One occurs simultaneously with the CPU spikes and lasts for 5 s. The other starts 26 s later and also completes within 5 s. According to our observations, starting the application (submitting the test vehicle parameters) before this time causes additional functions to be started up by the execution environment. After the warm-up phase finishes, we have 4

Figure 7: Evolution of in-application latency (top), working and backup edge node CPU (middle) and memory loads (bottom) in a representative offload situation. Displayed values are averaged to a 1 s measurement window.

instances of the Infer function on both edge nodes consuming approximately 279 MB of memory. At this point, the machine learning models used by the functions are loaded in memory, but they have not been used for supplying any inference. Starting the application at the 44th second of the test starts to feed the Infer function at E_w with images. This triggers an increase in the CPU and memory loads. CPU load settles in the 50%–60% range which is slightly higher than in the comparative case. Memory load increases by another 38 MB, which, in total, is still 157 MB less than in the baseline case. Both of these behaviors can be attributed to the fact that we start 4 functions instead of 7. Total inference and invocation delays appear to be steady with the first being approximately 52 ms which corresponds to the stabilized values seen at the baseline case. Performing the manual offload increases CPU and memory load values at E_b in a similar fashion while keeping latency values steady at 55 ms, on average. Looking at the memory consumption, we can estimate the contribution of one function instance as being 79 MB. This mostly corresponds with the observations made at E_b in the baseline case ($397 \text{ MB} = 5 \cdot 79 \text{ MB} + 2 \text{ MB}$), however, we see a higher difference when making this comparison with the 7 instances of E_w . While 7 instances used at their full potential should use $7 \cdot 79 \text{ MB} = 553 \text{ MB}$ of memory we see an allocation of only 473 MB. The difference can be explained based on what we observed in the warm-up case. By the time stability is reached, not all 7 function instances have gone through all of the three memory allocation phases as not all of them receive events to be processed.

In conclusion, we can say that while the warm-up process delays the application startup time, its benefits in CPU and memory load, as well as the stability of application latency outweigh this shortcoming. As for the CPU load, at warm-up, the burst of increased CPU load is much lower than without warm-up. Due to starting up fewer function instances, we can spare significant memory resources while keeping the application latency at a steady level.

6.4. Evaluation of the Node-Based Offload Controller

To evaluate the performance of the NBOC, we perform an automated offload and reversal cycle with warmed-up functions: we initiate 4 Grab Image and Infer functions and 2 Control One Vehicle instances, as discussed above. We offload the Infer function from E_w to E_b when the former’s CPU load reaches 85% and revert when the latter’s dips below 40%. First, we configure the NBOC to make a decision based on the average of the last 55 samples. With our CPU level sampling, this corresponds to approximately 15 s which is inspired by a naïve monitoring setup that we observed to have been utilized in industrial scenarios. It also provides results with a good visual separation compared to the other cases discussed later.

Fig. 8 shows inference latency and CPU load during a representative experiment. We plot both metrics using two aggregation options. With gray in the background, we provide an average using a 1 s time window, retrieved from the long-term storage of our TS. To provide better visibility on the trends, we also plot the 3 s averages in color, in the foreground. We

Figure 8: Inference latency (top) and edge node CPU load (bottom) while utilizing the SDE offloader. Offloading is triggered based on 55 samples of E_w CPU load. Figures show values averaged using 3 s (foreground, colored) and 1 s (background, gray) time windows.

start the experiment with a deployed and running application, that is, the Vehicle Connection Manager has already submitted the test vehicle configuration to the application. Initially, the application provides inference results with an average latency of 51 ms. Additionally to the base load, this puts a 56% average load on E_w 's CPU. At step 1, an additional load is placed on E_w which raises the level of the CPU usage to around 92% with some samples reaching 100%. Meanwhile, inference latency grows to 113 ms on average. As depicted in the bottom part of Fig. 8, 16.7 s pass while the NBOC's 55-sample-average reaches T_{offload} , at which point it instructs the application to invoke the already warmed-up Infer function instances on E_b (see step 2). As a result, the inference latency decreases to its previous values, and stabilizes at approximately 53 ms. CPU load on E_w decreases to 74% and increases to 43% on E_b . We remove the additional load from E_w at step 3, making its CPU level dip below T_{reversal} . This is picked up by the NBOC after 19.7 s and "moves" the Infer function back to E_w showing no significant difference in the inference latency (the average decreases by 2 ms).

In order to capture a wider set of offload performance characteristics, we provide a comparison based on multiple executions as well. To achieve this, we perform 150 offload/reversal cycles and we use the same baseline experiment as during the warm-up evaluation, i.e., we run the application for 30 minutes on E_w and E_b . In each of these cases, we capture the total latency observed by the application, i.e., from the time the Connect Vehicle function emits a trigger until the corresponding inference is interpreted by the Control One Vehicle function and it communicates its go/stop control message to the simulated vehicle. Fig. 9a shows the distribution of latency values

in the baseline measurement, for the last execution on E_w before offloading and for the first 1 second of execution on E_b after offloading. To ease the interpretation of trends in the data, we bin the values to 30 ms intervals, display them as percentages of the whole and provide an interpolation of the observed distributions.

Latency values in the baseline case correspond to the defined function execution times, invocation ratios and delays. Thanks to the warmed-up instances on E_w , average latency values captured during the first 1 s after the offloading event align with the distribution of the baseline. The measurements confirm that E_b , working as hot backup, can completely replace E_w without noticeable changes from the application's point of view. As the OC acts in a reactive fashion, the latency experienced by the last execution on E_w , on the other hand, should already suffer from the higher CPU load on E_w . Measurements support this assumption as these values are severely shifted towards higher latency ranges. While approximately 75% of the executions in the baseline or offloaded case remain under 125 ms, the third quartile for the last execution is 202 ms.

A possible option to improve latency during the last execution on E_w is to reduce the number of samples the NBOC tracks for triggering an offload. As our edge-based TS grants access to metrics on a per sample basis, we can achieve sub-second detection times as well. Fig. 9b displays a summary of the most extreme case where we utilize a trigger based on a single CPU load measurement sample. With this configuration, the first quartile of the last execution on E_w is 94 ms which is exactly halfway between the baseline's 65 ms and the previous configuration's 124 ms. Median and mean values also show a 17–21 ms improvement, while the third quartile remains basically unchanged. To further decrease the latency during the last execution, we need to reduce the reaction time of the OC. This can be attained by simplifying the decision mechanism and the communication patterns. The P4OC is designed to achieve this purpose.

6.5. Evaluation of the active P4 Offload Controller

To gauge the efficacy of our P4OC, we conduct two types of measurements. With the first, we give a peek into the Edge Resource Monitoring (ERM) protocol in use, and verify that sending out and processing its messages does not adversely affect the performance of the used P4 switch. With the second measurement type, we show that by leveraging the P4OC, we can achieve lower application latency during the last execution before offloading compared to what the NBOC is able to attain.

6.5.1. Networking aspects of the P4OC

Fig. 10 shows a Wireshark trace captured at the P4 switch registering both application traffic and ERM messages. It details the structure and the values of frame 6457, expanding the ERM extra-header on top of UDP port 12345. The shown message carries the actual CPU and memory load of E_w (Edge_ID = 1, Edge_CPU = 43%, Edge_mem = 88%). In addition, the capture shows the application packets forwarded by E_0 to either E_w or E_b . During the capture, packets are steered towards E_w since its CPU load is lower than T_{offload} .

(a) Trigger is defined on 55 CPU measurement samples.

(b) Trigger is defined on a single CPU measurement sample.

Figure 9: Distribution of the experienced end-to-end latency during the last function execution on E_w before being offloaded to E_b (blue) and during the first 1 s of operation on E_b (red) when using the Node-Based Offload Controller.

Fig. 11 depicts the distribution of the latency introduced by the P4 switch when normal application traffic packets are subject to different treatment. In our case, these are UDP packets, fragmented into multiple maximum transmission unit (MTU) sized (1480 byte) IP packets. The latency is computed by considering the time elapsed from reception at the input interface until transmission on the output port. Values are measured on the same transit packet via the Linux tcpdump application and repeated for 10k packets. When normal forwarding is enforced, the latency is experienced in the $[150, 500] \mu\text{s}$ range, the average intra-switch latency is $268 \mu\text{s}$ and the modal value (i.e., the frequency peak) is around $250 \mu\text{s}$. When ERM-based steering is applied, the latency distribution is shifted to $323 \mu\text{s}$ average with a more pronounced modal value peak of around $300 \mu\text{s}$. This means that the increased processing at the switch due to the ERM-based steering (involving an additional read operation from a memory register) impacts the latency with an average $50 \mu\text{s}$ additional contribution. Such impact is almost negligible at the end-to-end application layer, where we see delays of

Figure 10: Wireshark capture of ERM messages at the P4 switch.

Figure 11: Intra-switch application traffic latency distribution at the P4 switch.

30–125 ms during normal operation. Moreover, if implemented in programmable ASIC-based backends, in which typical latency values are in the order of $5 \mu\text{s}$ for bare metal switches and $20 \mu\text{s}$ for smart NICs [60], the additional contribution can be reduced to fractions of $1 \mu\text{s}$.

6.5.2. The effects of P4OC-driven offloading on application performance

Similarly to the NBOC's case, first we investigate a representative execution while utilizing the P4OC. Fig. 12 depicts this experiment in which the application is constantly configured to use the Infer function on E_w . It starts with the application running with a 55 ms inference latency causing a 55% CPU load on E_w . At step 1 we put E_w under stress and, visually at the same time, the offloading process is triggered. In the bottom-most chart of Fig. 12, we show results taken from the short-term TS storage that conserves measurement samples. Here we can observe that 60.57 s in our test, the Node Telemetry function records a CPU load of 52% which is considered normal. 341 ms later, at the next measurement point, it already encounters a CPU level of 96%, however. Latency values are also on the rise at this point, as we have four executions experiencing 94 ms, 109 ms, 77 ms and 76 ms delays, respectively.

Fig. 13 gives insight into what happens during the elevated CPU load. We can list three main constituents contributing to the delay increase, each of them being slowed down by the increased CPU load. Invocations leading up to the Infer function

Figure 12: Inference latency and edge node CPU load while utilizing the P4 Offload Controller. Charts on the top show values averaged using 3 s (foreground, colored) and 1 s (background, gray) time windows. The first function executed on node E_b is marked by an asterisk on the bottom-most figure.

(from the Connect Vehicle function) show slightly elevated values of 27 ms, 27 ms, 21 ms and 25 ms compared to the 21 ms average of the previous 3 s. The increase can be attributed to the R_{E_w} relay processing and forwarding the incoming calls slower. Datastore write also slows down to 16 ms, 24 ms, 8 ms and 5 ms, compared to the less than 2 ms average beforehand. In addition, the computing prowess of the Infer function takes a hit as well, registering 51 ms, 58 ms, 48 ms and 46 ms execution times (without datastore access) compared to the usual 32 ms average.

Sending in the CPU report of 96% to the P4OC, it immediately changes the path application traffic takes and diverts it towards E_b . As a result, the next function invocations already trigger an instance of the Infer function on E_b making the inference trigger, datastore write and Infer compute delay return to their normal values. This reduces the inference latency to 57 ms in the first second of running on E_b and keeps a 54 ms average while the function is run on E_b .

The fast offloading has the additional benefit that the CPU level at E_w jumps to above-threshold levels only for a sub-second time interval. This is short enough that it does not even register on our 1 s-average view retrieved from the long-term TS storage. Removing the additional load from E_w at the relative test time of 181 s provides a similarly smooth transition, enabling the application to continue with an inference latency of 53 ms in the remainder of the experiment. As Fig. 14 attests, no significant change is visible in any of the constituents.

Comparing the aggregated results of 150 offload/reversal cycles, shown in Fig. 15, to that of the NBOC using a single sampler condition (Fig. 9b), we can notice that the P4OC

Figure 13: Contribution of different factors to the inference latency during offloading utilizing the P4OC. The chart shows stacked values, the first function executed on node E_b is marked by an asterisk.

Figure 14: Contribution of different constituents to the inference latency during offload reversal with the P4OC. The first function executed on node E_w is marked by an asterisk.

can further reduce the experienced application latency. Now modal value peaks in all three cases align. Looking at the last execution on E_w , its first quartile drops 14 ms reaching 80 ms and the median is improved by 25 ms as well. While the third quartile is still high, having a value of 184 ms, it also improves on the NBOC's 200 ms.

As this comparison attests, moving the OC closer to the infrastructure level and shortening the communication path clearly improves the reaction time of the OC. However, as shown in Fig. 13, the rising CPU load between two detection points can already have adverse effects on the application, especially if it has a high invocation rate, as in our case. We see two possibilities to overcome this issue: increasing the CPU load sampling rate and predicting the rise of the CPU load. With the current CPU monitor built into the Node Telemetry function, sampling the CPU at a higher rate is not possible without actively contributing to the observable CPU load. Implementing a more efficient CPU monitor can help in this aspect. Our test cases emulate scenarios where a process starts to generate a sudden high load at a random point in time. While predicting such occurrences based on solely the previous CPU usage seems to be infeasible, incorporating other metrics as well might enable the use of a predictive model. Dealing with situations where load shows periodicity or gradual increase is also an area where predictive methods can be leveraged. Pairing the low-latency offload mechanism with these improvements, in our view, can further improve application latency before offloading or can even completely eradicate the performance degradation seen in our results.

Figure 15: Distribution of the experienced end-to-end latency during the last function execution on E_w before being offloaded to E_b (blue) and during the first 1 s of operation on E_w (red) when using the P4 Offload Controller triggered by a single event.

7. Conclusion

In this paper, we demonstrated a tool that builds on and extends AWS services to deploy and run serverless functions and migrates the compute tasks wrapped inside them in edge environments. We note again that our concept is not restrictive to AWS and could be generalized to other providers or serverless environments. We provided two different methods for moving the application compute tasks between edge nodes. To eliminate function cold start delays, we incorporated warm-up capabilities into our execution environment and evaluated these functionalities using a vehicle remote control application and monitoring the CPU load of the edge nodes. We have shown that warm-up can significantly reduce total memory consumption and eliminate latency spikes during migration. We have also shown that our offloading mechanisms are viable with our P4 Offload Controller being the faster. Upon migration, the P4OC managed to add *no* observable extra latency in our sample application. This is due to cutting the communication overhead and employing function warm-up which is unique in the context of the surveyed literature and latency-bounded edge services as well as being an outstanding result.

During our evaluations, we identified multiple aspects of our work that can be improved in the future. The reaction time of both of our offload controllers could be decreased by applying more frequent CPU measurements, more efficient metrics collection, and handling of sub-second, time-based queries in the Telemetry Service. The P4OC could be extended with capabilities of being triggered with multiple metrics, similarly to the NBOC. In our view, this direction can also lead to the ability to handle more than two edge nodes, not just in backup roles, with a significant delay between them. Adding active delay discovery between the edge nodes could reveal their distance from each other which we could take into consideration in complex NBOC offload trigger conditions. For now, our P4OC implementation is constrained to fixed trigger parameters, however, this together with the ERM protocol can also be extended

to support multiple custom metrics with more complex trigger conditions. Placing an upper-level placement optimization entity (similarly to that discussed in our previous work [52]) could also help in configuring any of the offload controllers and even substitute active delay monitoring, to a certain degree. Modifying the P4OC could also provide us capabilities of analyzing application traffic and steering based on that or load sharing between edge nodes.

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